

Lucas sequence and Fibonacci triads of graphs for analysis of charge transfer spectra of complexes of a series of methylated indoles

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Abstract : Recursive use of Lucas sequences and Fibonacci triads of graphs in a complete perturbational molecular orbital (PMO) calculation is shown to be convenient in obtaining expressions for the HOMO energies of a series of methylated indoles in terms of the inductive effect PMO parameter (h_{Me}) of the methyl group. Correlating such expressions with the experimental charge transfer transition energies of the series of TCNE-indole molecular complexes, h_{Me} for the methyl group is determined in a straightforward way and the value thus obtained is close to the one recommended by Streitwieser on the basis of other spectroscopic evidences.

Keywords : Graph theory, Lucas sequence, Fibonacci triad, inductive effect, molecular complexes, charge transfer.

Introduction

In chemistry graph theory has many fields of application¹, namely, isomer enumeration², study of conjugated molecules³⁻⁷, counts of Kekulé structure^{8,9} and Clar sextets^{10,11} as measures of aromaticity, theoretical investigation of fullerenes¹², quantitative structure activity relationships¹³ etc. Fibonacci numbers are long known^{14,15} to belong to a sequence in which any number is obtained as the sum of the previous two numbers (excepting the first two) :

$$F_0 = 0, F_1 = 1 \text{ and } F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}, n \geq 2 \quad (1)$$

This sequence was found to occur in the topological Hosoya index¹⁶ of graphs. More recently, this sequence is finding applications in Kekulé structure counts of hexagon networks useful for the study of carbon nano-structures¹⁷. A group of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons are defined as Fibonacenes^{18,19} because their Kekulé structure counts coincide with the Fibonacci numbers. El-Basil first showed^{20,21} that the matching and characteristic polynomials of large graphs can be constructed by a 'building up' procedure starting from smaller graphs through the use of Fibonacci triads and Lucas sequences of graphs.

A Fibonacci triad (FT) of graphs is defined²⁰ as a set of graphs $\{G_1, G_2, G_3\}$ such that the subgraphs $(G_3 - G_2, G_3 - G_1, G_2 - G_1)$ consist only of a single vertex and a K_2 subgraph (i.e. a graph with two vertices joined by an edge). Here $G_i - G_j$ means a subgraph obtained by pruning G_j out of G_i . Two sequences of graphs are shown in

Fig. 1. Three Fibonacci triads of graphs.

Fig. 1 which consists of three Fibonacci triads, FT(1), FT(2) and FT(3). A sequence of graphs $\{g_i\}$, having a common subgraph g , is said to be a Lucas sequence (LS)²⁰ if the set of graphs $\{g_1 - g, g_2 - g, g_3 - g, \dots\}$ is the sequence of cycles, $\{C_m, C_{m+1}, C_{m+2}, \dots\}$ (where C_p means a cycle with p vertices). Examples are given in Fig. 2 where the graphs g_a, g_b, g_c are in a Lucas sequence (LS1) because $g_a - g, g_b - g$ and $g_c - g$, where g is a single vertex shown in bracket, are respectively C_3, C_4, C_5 . Similarly for LS2 and LS3 the common subgraphs to be pruned are linear chains with two and four vertices respectively.

Fig. 2. Three Lucas sequences of graphs.

The matching numbers $p(k)$ of the graphs in an FT are related^{16,20} by the recurrence relation,

$$p(G_3, k + 1) = p(G_2, k + 1) + p(G_1, k) \quad (2)$$

The matching numbers of the graphs in LS obey²¹ the recurrence relation,

$$p(g_{m+2}, k + 1) = p(g_{m+1}, k + 1) + p(g_m, k) \quad (3)$$

These numbers are the unsigned coefficients of the acyclic polynomial²² of the corresponding graph. For a general graph G with matching numbers $p(k)$, the acyclic polynomial is given by

$$P^{AC}(G; x) = \sum_{k=0}^{[n/2]} (-1)^k p(k) x^{n-2k} \quad (4)$$

where n is the total number of vertices in G and $[n/2]$ is the highest integer not greater than $n/2$.

The characteristic polynomial (CP) of G is obtained by adding the contribution of the cyclic components to the acyclic polynomial.

There are, however, only very little reports^{23,24} on use of El-Basil's FT-LS method of constructing CPs for molecular orbital calculations. The FT-LS method builds up the CPs of the necessary graphs in a sequential manner. The objective of the present paper is to show that since the graphs and subgraphs needed for a perturbational molecular orbital (PMO) calculation by graph theory on a family of molecules are included in such sequences, the method is of great practical utility in streamlining PMO calculations and that such calculations may be used to interpret the experimentally observed trends in charge transfer (CT) transition energies of molecular complexes (also called 'electron donor acceptor (EDA) complexes').

The EDA complexes under study

The systems under study are π -type EDA complexes of indole, and a series of methylated indoles with tetracyanoethylene (TCNE). In a series of methylated indoles the inductive (+I) effect of the methyl group is expected to cause the π -donor ability of the indoles to vary, depending on the number and position of the methyl group attached to the π -conjugated atoms of the rings. This variation should be reflected in the variation of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energies of the indoles and also in the variation of CT transition energies of their EDA complexes with a given acceptor. While the former can be calculated theoretically, the other is observed experimentally, and therefore, a correlation is expected. For an EDA complex the CT transition energy is given by the well known²⁵ McConnell-Ham-Platt equation,

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_D - E_A - \Delta \quad (5)$$

where I_D is the vertical ionization potential of the donor, E_A is the vertical electron affinity of the acceptor and Δ is a term coming from non-bonding species, solvation etc. Eq. (5) was later given a theoretical basis by Mulliken²⁶. The main part of Δ comes from the electro-

static interactions between the positively charged donor and the negatively charged acceptor in the excited state²⁶. If in an experiment the acceptor is kept fixed and the donor is varied in a particular solvent, eq. (5) takes the form,

$$h\nu_{CT} = -E_j + \text{constant} \quad (6)$$

where E_j is the HOMO energy of the donor.

In a series of methylated indoles E_j can be expressed in terms of the inductive effect Hückel parameter h_{Me} of the methyl group²⁷ using the Coulson-Longuet-Higgins perturbational molecular orbital (PMO) method²⁸ as follows :

$$E_j = E_j^0 + h_{Me}\beta \sum_r C_{rj}^2 \quad (7)$$

where E_j^0 is the energy of the j -th MO of the unperturbed system (here, the indole molecule with no methyl substitution) and β is the $C(sp^2) - C(sp^2)$ resonance integral in benzene. The parameters h_{Me} determines the perturbation in the Coulomb integral (α) resulting from attachment of Me-group to an sp^2 -C atom by the relations²⁷,

$$\alpha' = \alpha + h_{Me}\beta \quad (8)$$

In eq. (8) the prime indicates values after perturbation. The quantity C_{rj} in eq. (7) is the r -th component of the eigenvector corresponding to the j -th MO of the unperturbed system. As usual in the Hückel MO theory, α is taken as the zero of energy and since E_j^0 in the series of methylated indoles is constant, eqs. (7) and (8) can be combined as

$$h\nu_{CT} = -h_{Me}\beta \sum_r C_{rj}^2 + \text{constant} \quad (9)$$

The perturbational quantity appearing in eq. (9) can be obtained graph theoretically as shown in the next sections.

Graph theoretical calculation of the perturbational quantities needed for the present series of indoles

The atom labels in the molecular structure of indole are shown in Fig. 3. The hydrogen-suppressed molecular graph of indole is the weighted graph $G^{(W)}$ (Fig. 3) in which one vertex and two edges are weighted due to the presence of the heteroatom, nitrogen. The vertex labels

Fig. 3. Molecular structure of indole and H-suppressed graph of indole and its isoconjugate.

of $G^{(W)}$, not shown in Fig. 3, are the same as those in the molecular structure. The characteristic polynomial (CP) of the graph $G^{(W)}$ is given by

$$P(G^{(W)}; x) = P(G_{iso}; x) - hP(G^{(W)} - v_1; x) \quad (10)$$

where G_{iso} is the graph obtained from $G^{(W)}$ by ignoring the self-loop of weight h and $G^{(W)} - v_1$ is the subgraph obtained by deleting the vertex labeled 1. If a vertex is deleted from a graph, the result is called an Ulam subgraph²⁹. The square of the r -th component of an eigenvector of a graph G corresponding to the j -th eigenvalue

Fig. 4. Ulam subgraphs and another necessary subgraph for the present calculations.

is given³⁰ by,

$$C_{ij}^2 = \frac{P(G - v_r; x)}{d[P(G; x)]/dx} \text{ at } x = x_j \quad (11)$$

where $G - v_r$ is the r -th Ulam subgraph of G . For the present series of methylated indoles we need the Ulam subgraphs U_i , $i = 1$ to 4, shown in Fig. 4. It can be readily recognized that most of the graphs and subgraphs needed for the present calculation are members of the FTs and LSs taken in Figs. 1 and 2. Thus, G_{iso} is the same as g_n and U_1 coincides with G_4 . The CPs of U_2 and U_3 can be expanded as

$$P(U_2; x) = P(G_6; x) - hxP(G_3; x) \quad (12)$$

$$P(U_3; x) = P(G_4; x) - hxP(G_2; x) \quad (13)$$

The $p(k)$ numbers of a finite linear chain L_n with n vertices is given by the combinatorial formula

$$p(L_n, k) = {}^{n-k}C_k, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, [n/2] \quad (14)$$

This can be utilized to find the $p(k)$ numbers of G_1 and G_5 ; for the cycle G_2 the numbers can be easily obtained by direct counting. For all the other graphs in the FTs of Fig. 1 the recurrence relation (2) can be applied as shown in Table 1. Similarly eq. (3) can be utilized to obtain the $p(k)$ numbers of the graphs in the LSs of Fig. 2, starting from the small graphs g_a, g_b and g_d ; these are shown in

Table 1. Calculation of $p(k)$ numbers of the graphs in FT1, FT2 and FT3

	$p(0)$	$p(1)$	$p(2)$	$p(3)$	$p(4)$
G_1	1	4	3	0	0
G_2	1	6	9	2	0
G_3	1	7	13	5	0
G_4	1	8	19	14	2
G_5	1	5	6	1	0
G_3	1	7	13	5	0
G_6	1	8	18	11	1

Table 2. Calculation of $p(k)$ numbers of the graphs in LS1, LS2 and LS3

	$p(0)$	$p(1)$	$p(2)$	$p(3)$	$p(4)$
g_a	1	6	6	0	0
g_b	1	7	11	2	0
g_c	1	8	17	8	0
g_a	1	6	6	0	0
g_d	1	7	11	3	0
g_e	1	8	17	9	0
g_f	1	9	24	20	3
g_c	1	8	17	8	0
g_f	1	9	24	20	3
g_h	1	10	32	37	11

Table 2. The acyclic polynomials of the required graphs, constructed by using these $p(k)$ numbers in eq. (4), are shown in Table 3.

The characteristic polynomials of the graphs can now be constructed by adding the contributions of the rings. As an illustration the ring contributions of G_{iso} are shown in Fig. 5. For the other necessary graphs the ring contributions are given in Table 4 together with that for G_{iso} . The CPs of the necessary graphs and subgraphs are listed in Table 5. The vertex and edge-weights due to N are the

Table 3. Acyclic polynomials of the necessary graphs and subgraphs

Graph	Acyclic polynomial
$G_{\text{iso}} = g_h$	$x^9 - 10x^7 + 32x^5 - 37x^3 + 11x$
$U_1 = G_4$	$x^8 - 8x^6 + 19x^4 - 14x^2 + 2$
$U_2 = G_6 - hG_3$	$x^8 - 8x^6 + 18x^4 - 11x^2 + 1 - h(x^7 - 7x^5 + 13x^3 - 14x^2 - 5x)$
$U_3 = G_4 - hx.G_2$	$x^8 - 8x^6 + 19x^4 - 14x^2 + 2 - hx(x^6 - 6x^4 + 9x^2 - 5)$

Fig. 5. Ring contributions to the CP of G_{iso} .

Graph	Ring contribution to CP
$G_{\text{iso}} = g_h$	$(-1)^1 2^1 x^{9-5} + 3 \times [(-1)^2 2^1 x^{9-7}] + 2 \times [(-1)^3 2^1 x^{9-9}] + (-1)^1 2^1 x^{9-6} + 2 \times [(-1)^2 2^1 x^{9-8}]$
$U_1 = G_4$	$(-1)^1 2^1 x^{8-6} + (-1)^2 2^1 x^{8-8}$
$U_2 = G_6 - hG_3$	$(-1)^1 2^1 x^{8-6} - h \times (-1)^1 2^1 x^{7-6}$
$U_3 = G_4 - hx \cdot G_2$	$(-1)^1 2^1 x^{8-6} + (-1)^2 2^1 x^{8-8} - hx \times (-1)^1 2^1 x^{6-6}$

heteroatom Hückel parameters : $h = h_N = 1.0$ and $k = k_{\text{CN}} = 1.0$ (as recommended by Streitwieser²⁷).

There are five changes of sign in the expression for $P(G^{(W)}; x)$. Moreover, the adjacency matrix is hermitian, and all its eigenvalues are real. Hence out of the nine zeros of $P(G^{(W)}; x)$ five are positive and four are negative. In other words, five HOMO energy eigenvalues (in β unit) of indole are positive and four are negative. As indole molecule has ten π -electrons, the lowest positive

Table 5. Characteristics polynomials of the necessary graphs and subgraphs

Graph	Characteristics polynomial
$G_{\text{iso}} = g_h$	$x^9 - 10x^7 + 32x^5 - 2x^4 - 39x^3 + 6x^2 + 15x - 4$
$U_1 = G_4$	$x^8 - 8x^6 + 19x^4 - 16x^2 + 4$
$U_2 = G_6 - hG_3$	$x^8 - x^7 - 8x^6 + 7x^5 + 18x^4 - 13x^3 - 13x^2 + 7x + 1$
$U_3 = G_4 - hx \cdot G_2$	$x^8 - x^7 - 8x^6 + 6x^5 + 19x^4 - 9x^3 - 16x^2 + 4x + 4$
$G^{(W)}$	$x^9 - x^8 - 10x^7 + 8x^6 + 32x^5 - 21x^4 - 39x^3 + 22x^2 + 15x - 8$

eigenvalue corresponds to the HOMO which can be located by using the Budan-Fourier theorem³¹. This theorem states that if all zeros of a polynomial $P(x)$ of degree n are real, the number of zeros lying in the interval (a, b) , $a < b$, is equal to $N(a) - N(b)$, where $N(a)$ is the number of sign-changes in the sequence $P(a), P^1(a), P^2(a), \dots, P^n(a)$ with $P^m(a)$ denoting the m -th derivative of $P(x)$ at $x = a$; $N(b)$ has a similar meaning.

With $P(G^{(W)}; x)$ and its nine derivatives it can be readily verified that $N(0) = 5$, $N(0.5) = 5$ and $N(0.55) = 4$. Hence according to the Budan-Fourier theorem there is no zero of $P(G^{(W)}; x)$ in $(0, 0.5)$ and one zero in $(0.5, 0.55)$. The HOMO energy (in β unit), therefore, lies in $(0.5, 0.55)$. Now starting with 0.55, the desired zero of $P(G^{(W)}; x)$ is found, after only two Newton-Raphson iterations, to converge at 0.52014. This is the HOMO energy of indole and we call it x_5 , after arranging the eigenvalues of $G^{(W)}$ in the decreasing sequence x_1, x_1, \dots, x_9 .

Correlation of the graph theoretically obtained perturbational quantities with experimental CT transition energies

Molecular complexes of indole and methylated indoles with TCNE in dichloromethane medium exhibit charge transfer (CT) absorption and their CT transition energies, collected from literature³² are given in Table 6 together with the perturbational coefficients calculated graph theoretically by the present FT-LS method. Fig. 6 shows

that the plot of $h\nu_{\text{CT}}$ against $\sum_r C_r^2$ is linear, with a correlation coefficient of -0.98 and the linear regression equation is

$$h\nu_{CT} = -1.4768 \sum_r C_{r^5}^2 + 2.4665 \quad (15)$$

When this is compared with eq. (9) it is found that $h_{Me} = -0.48$ (taking $\beta = -3.1$ eV from the first four singlet-singlet transitions of benzene), close to Strietwieser's²⁷ recommended value for Me-group : $h_{Me} = -0.5$. The negative slope in Fig. 6 indicates that the HOMO energy systematically increases with increase in number of methyl groups and with variation of their location with re-

Table 6. CT transition energies of complexes of indole and methylated indoles with TCNE in dichloromethane medium

Donor	$\sum_r C_{r^5}^2$	$h\nu_{CT}$ (eV)
Indole	0	2.472
1-Methyl indole	0.1392	2.364
2-Methyl indole	0.1095	2.230
1,2-Dimethyl indole	0.2487	2.051
2,3-Dimethyl indole	0.4068	1.880

Fig. 6. Plot of CT transition energy against calculated perturbational quantities.

spect to the indole ring, thereby lowering the CT transition energy systematically in the series. The present graph theoretical calculation using FT-LS method thus rationalizes the variation of CT transition energy in the series of methylated indole-TCNE complexes and also quantifies the inductive effect of the Me-group by yielding a reasonable value of h_{Me} .

References

1. L. R. Foulds, "Graph Theory Applications", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1992.
2. L. M. Masinter, N. S. Sridharan, J. Lederberg and D. H. Smith, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 7702.
3. D. C. Mukherjee, K. Datta and A. K. Mukherjee, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2001, **40A**, 126.
4. A. Graovac, I. Gutman and N. Trinajstić, "Topological Approach to the Chemistry of Conjugated Molecules", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1977.
5. N. Bej, D. C. Mukherjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Mol. Phys.*, 2003, **101**, 865.
6. S. M. Patra, R. K. Mishra and B. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1996, **35A**, 813.
7. J. R. Dias, "Molecular Orbital Calculations using Chemical Graph Theory", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1993.
8. S. J. Cyvin and I. Gutman, "Kekulé Structures in Benzenoid Hydrocarbons", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1988.
9. A. T. Balaban and I. Tomescu, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1984, **57**, 391.
10. D. J. Klein, T. G. Schmalz, G. E. Hite, A. Metropoulos and W. A. Seitz, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1985, **120**, 367.
11. A. T. Balaban and T. G. Schmalz, *J. Chem. Inf. Model*, 2006, **46**, 1563.
12. G. E. Hite, T. P. Zivkovic and D. J. Klein, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **74**, 349.
13. I. Gutman, Z. Tomvic, B. K. Mishra and M. Kuanar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2001, **40A**, 4.
14. N. N. Vorobév, "Fibonacci Numbers", Blaisdell, New York, 1961.
15. V. E. Hoggat, "The Fibonacci and Lucas Numbers", Haughton, Boston, 1969.
16. H. Hosoya, *Fibonacci Quart.*, 1973, **11**, 255.
17. H. Hosoya, *Forma*, 2004, **19**, 405.
18. A. T. Balaban, *MATCH Commun. Math. Chem.*, 1989, **24**, 29.
19. I. Gutman and S. Klavžarb, *MATCH Commun. Math. Comput. Chem.*, 2006, **55**, 39.
20. S. El-Basil, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **65**, 191.
21. S. El-Basil, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **65**, 199.
22. I. Gutman, *Publ. Inst. Math. (Beograd)*, 1977, **22**, 63.
23. A. K. Mukherjee and J. Sarkar, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1994, **106**, 65.
24. J. Sarkar and A. K. Mukherjee, *Int. J. Quant. Chem.*, 1997, **63**, 817.
25. H. McConnell, J. Ham and J. R. Platt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 66.
26. R. S. Mulliken and W. B. Person, *Annu. Rev. Phys.*

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Chem., 1962, **13**, 107.

27. A. Streitwieser (Jr.), "Molecular Orbital Theory for Organic Chemists", Wiley, New York, 1961, Chap. 5.
28. C. A. Coulson and H. C. Longuet-Higgins, *Proc. Royal Soc. (London)*, 1947, **A191**, 39.
29. S. M. Ulam, "A Collection of Mathematical Problems", Wiley, New York, 1960.
30. A. K. Mukherjee and K. K. Datta, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1989, **101**, 499.
31. A. G. Kurosh, "Higher Algebra", Nauka, Moscow, 1969.
32. R. Foster and P. Hanson, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 255.

